

DESIGNING AN EDUCATIONAL MANAGEMENT MODEL PROCESS IN THE PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION SYSTEM

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Annotation: This article describes designing an educational management model process in the professional education system, its main features, characteristics and definitions of the main terms.

Key words: management, model, education, economy, standards, program, teacher, pedagogue, planning, control, analysis, evaluation

In this article, the construction of a management model of the educational process will be carried out to implement the basic professional educational program of the professional education (here in after - BPEP PE). For this it is necessary identify key processes aimed at implementing BPEP and also highlight the criteria and performance indicators of the management model of PE.

Analysis of processes that are directly related to implementation BPEP PE, analysis of the works of B.I. Gerasimova, E.B. Gerasimova, M.Z. Svitkina, A.Yu. Sizikina, S.A. Stepanova et al. allows us to identify several groups processes necessary to build a management model: basic work processes, management processes, as well as processes providing educational activities. It follows that the management model of the educational process should cover three groups of processes.

We will take a closer look at each of them. The group of main work processes in the study includes itself educational process, the direct result of which is graduation of specialists from professional education. Accordingly, it includes the types of activities necessary for training a specialist who meets the needs of the economy of the region and consumer requirements.

The group "management processes" includes such activities as analysis and evaluation of all data received by process managers. The result of the management process is designated as "increased effectiveness and efficiency of the main and supporting processes" [1] It should also be noted that to manage the BPEP PE, it is necessary to assess all available resources (personnel, material, technical, information, etc.). Their performance should be sufficient to ensure the implementation of BPEP PE.

All resources for the implementation of BPEP PE are included in the group "supporting processes". Human resources must match requirements that are imposed by GES PE, namely to own competencies sufficient to solve the tasks assigned to them: - training of a specialist corresponding to real conditions modern economy. Thus, we can say that the result processes ensuring the educational process is the creation sufficient conditions for the implementation of basic and management processes. In the logic of the process approach, the diagram is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 - Scheme of processors for implementing BPEP PE

The studies of theory and practice of problems presented in the work professional education demonstrate that scientists and practitioners are making attempts to establish effective technologies controls that will allow for minimal congestion in all groups processes to achieve the main result of an educational institution - training of personnel that meets the needs of all consumer groups (regional economy, parents, students). To analyze the content, structure and processes of impact on educational process, in this study, a special block of implementation of the professional educational process education - “management processes”, it will allow identifying deviations, and also adjust them to achieve better results.

As can be seen from Figure 2, management is a set of processes that are aimed at developing, accepting and implementing management decisions, in this regard we can conclude that management will consist of the activities of all its subjects, which relate to the supporting process aimed at changing characteristics, qualities of control objects, that is, directly educational process.

From the point of view of the systems approach, management is considered as a system where structural elements are management functions. Based on on research by T.Yu. Bazarova, V.V. Lukashovich, M.M. Potashnik, T.A. Salimova, P.I. Tretyakov's structural elements include: -“planning - determining goals, means and criteria for achieving them; -organization - formation and improvement of interaction between control and managed systems to implement plans, defining responsibility and authority; -management - staging assignments to subordinates, analysis of the state of the team, performance evaluation subordinates, making decisions about rewards and punishments, etc. (essentially creation of a motivational environment); -control - collecting information about the process fulfillment of aimed plans (etc.)” [2].

In essence, all these functions make up the management cycle, which research results of Yu.A. Konarzhevsky, is understood as “holistic a set of interacting management functions, oriented towards achieving a specific goal and carried out series or parallel”. It is worth noting that at the same time the management function will be viewed “as a relationship between control system and managed object, requiring control system to perform a certain action to ensure purposefulness and (or) organization of controlled processes” . [3] Through feedback mechanism carried out interaction of subjects and objects of process

management, due to which the control subject has a complete information picture about actions and results of the control object. The interactions are shown in Figure 2. where, using arrows, the management cycle is displayed. When its connections with the control object are effective, the control system is effective and holistic [4]. Thus, in the educational management model the process must include control objects.

Figure 2 - Cycle of management of the educational process in professional education

The control cycle shown in Figure 2 is formed from control functions, we will look at each of them in more detail.

Function “planning” at the level of management of the implementation of BPEP PE represents the activities of the head of the BPEP and the subjects management which should be aimed at assessing the capabilities resources, as well as achieving results determined by the requirements consumers and GES PE. The result of the function is the composition plans for various activities.

It should also be noted that the planning process can be divided into two main stages or directions, namely:

- 1) strategic planning, which allows to determine strategy for the development of activities for the implementation of BPEP PE;
- 2) operational planning, which allows to determine tactics actions to implement the planned strategy.

So, according to S.A. Stepanov, a significant difference strategic planning from traditional approaches is that in this planning it is necessary to “go from the future to the present, and not from the past to the future” [5]. This approach to planning involves predicting changes, and not just analyzing previous ones errors made during the implementation of activities. Analysis of specialized literature showed that when implementing the function “strategic planning” should address the following issues: -determining the desired future state of the control system educational process, main achievements and key problems educational process; -determination of basic directions of development management of the educational process in accordance with the established strategic goals; - determination of a system of criteria and indicators for all areas of activity.

The “organization” block as a function of the management model implementation educational process in the implementation of BPEP PE, assumes identification of management subjects, their content of activities, powers, as well as the level of responsibility.

In order to have an idea of responsibility and powers of officials in the implementation of BPEP PE is necessary review the work regulations. The main difference between the work regulations officials from the job description of a specific employee is that in this case it is possible to determine horizontal interaction of performers and specify the result activities, as well as determine the indicators of this result.

In this study, work was done to form regulations for the interaction of employees of an educational organization during implementation of BPEP PE. To formulate the regulations, we took into account key areas of activity of the main management processes, and exactly:

1. Preparation of educational and planning documentation for implementation BPEP.
2. Educational and methodological support for the implementation of BPEP (training disciplines and interdisciplinary courses).
3. Development individual professional personal trajectory of achieving educational results.
4. Organization and control of the liquidation of academic debts.
5. Organization of training for students according to an individual schedule.
6. Organization and control of training and production practices.
7. Organization and control of course design.
8. Organization and control of the implementation of educational and research projects students' works as part of extracurricular independent work on BPEP elements.
9. Organization and control of tests and differentiated credits in academic disciplines, interdisciplinary courses and professional modules.
10. Organization and control of the state final graduate certifications.

Each of these types of activities for the implementation of educational process, an activity criterion was defined, a process that should be implemented to achieve its results. Also for each process an executor of the process has been appointed with a deadline for completing this or that other work. In order to effectively document the regulations of activity, regulatory documents have been defined, which are necessary to complete the process, and also specified documents (input, output) accompanying this process. To design a model for managing the educational process subjects of management are defined: student, employer, BPEP manager, methodologist, educational unit manager, social pedagogue, teacher.

"Management" function when implementing the management model educational process, from the point of view of M.M. Potashnik, must provide "the interest of all participants in the educational activities with their labor, maintain a favorable moral psychological climate in the team" [6]. Such actions presuppose first of all, working with all participants in educational activities aimed at the motivational component of management, which should be based on a study of the needs of management subjects.

Management activity is an activity that is based on constant planning and analysis, formation of optimal conditions for all participants in the process. In the works of T.V. Ashlapova, V. Vroom, Yu.V. Yesenkova, A. Maslov, M.M. Potashnik, B.C. Suvorov, F. Herzberg and etc. it is noted that in order to implement effective management, the holder processes, you must be able to determine the motivations of your subordinates, be able to create an activity environment that will allow achieving results in full. This requires a variety of assessment methods. performance results of teachers, introduce forms of encouragement, optimal for each employee.

Taking into account the above, the essence of the “leadership” function is based on the daily work of management subjects with all participants in educational activities without exception to achieve the goals.

The “control” function is implemented on the basis of monitoring, i.e. constant monitoring of educational results and verification of them compliance with intermediate or final operational requirements goals. Control of educational activities is carried out through management activities; and is aimed at implementing feedback between the subject of management and the object of management.

The features of the “control” function of the educational process can be include the fact that during monitoring it is necessary to evaluate the predicted result, implementation of basic, supporting and management BPEP PE processes, their quality indicators, intermediate, current, finite and distant in time. Thus, the function "control" in managing the educational process involves analysis and correction of activities aimed at improving results. Implementation of control functions for head of BPEP involves organizing staffing for educational process; creating conditions for the implementation of individual professional personal trajectory of achieving educational results (IPPTAER); organization of educational and methodological support IPPTAER; monitoring the implementation of curriculum schedules.

The methodologist in his activities must ensure the following areas of activity:
-creation of educational and methodological complexes BPEP elements;
- organization of internal examination of teaching materials management elements BPEP;
- creation and updating of educational and methodological resources in compliance with professional standards and GES requirements; -placement of educational and methodological materials in a remote environment training.

To implement the educational process, the subject of the management model educational process - the educational unit manager performs the following functions:

1. Creation of curriculum schedules.
 2. Maintenance of curriculum calendars.
 3. Providing optimal conditions for the implementation of calendar curriculum schedules.
- In turn, the social teacher must exercise control student attendance and progress, as well as coordinate achievement of educational results by students studying individual educational plans. For a teacher in the educational process management model The following functions are assigned:

1. Organization of achievement of educational results by students.
2. Creation of funds of assessment tools taking into account the requirements of professional standards and GES.
3. Providing the educational process with educational integration and extracurricular activities.

The presented description of the management cycle is focused on result in the formation of a specialist who will satisfy requirements of GES PE, as well as the needs of the regional economy.

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